

Translation methods in the translation of jewelry terms

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Annotation

This article provides information on methods of translating jewelry terms in Uzbek and English. At the same time, a broad understanding of translation methods is given. Non-substitute translation methods and realia are also widely covered.

Key words: jewelry terms, acus, aigrette, bandeau, benoiton, comb, coronet, diadem, resilla, sarpech, tillabargak, bodomoy, zebigardon, shokila, qushduo, haykal, bozuband, tavq;

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена информация о методах перевода ювелирных терминов на узбекский и английский языки. При этом дается широкое понимание методов перевода, а также широко освещаются методы и реалии беззамещающего перевода.

Ключевые слова: Ювелирные термины, бандо, бенуитон, гребень, корона, диадема, резилла, сарпеч, тиллабаргак, бодомой, зебигардон, шокила, кушдуо, хайкал, бозубанд, тавк;

Introduction

This article reveals to translate some jewelry lexemes in English and Uzbek languages. It is given that jewelry terms can be translated by means of transliteration, transcription, and calque. Information is given about the realia that exist in the language.

Translation methods of some jewelry terms in English Uzbek language.

Translation is a form of international communication. Translation has been around since ancient times. Translation is one of the oldest types of human activity, and for centuries different nations have been aware of the changes in the society of other nations due to this field. It has literary and scientific types. Translation is to reveal the meaning of a text existing in one language by turning it into a second language while preserving its form and content. It is very important to keep the originality in the translation. For this reason, patience, research, and knowledge are required from the translator. When a translator chooses to translate a work in another language, he is required to acquire knowledge and skills about the spirituality, culture and life of that nation. This is a long

process. Dictionaries are mainly used to translate any word or expression in order to give a full explanation of the given term or lexeme.

As a result of scientific research, we have obtained the following information about the ancient types of hair and head jewelry in English. Old English hair and headdress types: acus, aigrette, bandeau, barrette, benoiton, billiment, bodkin, comb, coronet, crown-headdress, diadem, ferrenniere, hairpin, hatpin, resilla, sarpech, wreath.

Acus - "akus" is a Roman hairpin used to secure the hairstyle. It is 6 to 9 inches long and made of gold, silver, bone, wood, or ivory. Has decorative patterns. The Ancient Greek and Roman Dictionary says that it is similar to a sewing needle. In the sources, there is information that in addition to its use as jewelry, it was also used to fasten clothes. In all sources, this ancient jewel is presented in the form of akus, that is, it is translated by the method of transliteration.

Aigrette - an egret is represented by a feather. The name comes from the bird's feather used for hair and headdresses. This ornament was used as an ornament for hair and hats. This tradition was widespread in the 19th century.

Bandeau - bandeau or headband. Sources say that this jewelry was popular in the Middle Ages in 1825-1835. It consists of strands of pearls or pearls, which are passed across the forehead and attached to the hairstyle at the back. In the later periods, the thread was replaced by metal jewelry.

Barrette is a hair ornament reminiscent of a barrette. It is tightly clamped to the hair. In the middle of the beret there is a bar that is attached to the opposite side. It is because of this that the hair is caught with tension.

Benoiton is a jewelry consisting of several chains that hang down from the hair. This style became popular after Victoria Sardou (1831-1908) wrote the comedy "La Famille Benoiton" in 1866.

Billiment - billiment or habilment is an ornament worn near the forehead in the Middle Ages.

Comb – A patterned ornament that is pinned to the hair as an ornament. These are crown-shaped combs of the 15th century. Combs are made of metal, horn, bone, ivory.

A coronet is a crown worn by noblemen at state ceremonies. They are mainly made of precious metals or gold.

Crown A circular headdress usually made of gold and decorated with precious stones, worn as a sign of royalty. They are reserved for reigning monarchs.

A diadem is a band-style headpiece worn on the forehead. In ancient times, both men and women wore this jewelry. The term diadem is Greek for "to bind around". In

the 19th century, this jewelry became popular again as a symbol of commercial and industrial wealth.

A *ferroniere* is an elegant piece of jewelry worn on the forehead by women to help hold the hairstyle in place. It consists of a thin chain or textile thread, usually with a single gemstone in the center. The name comes from a painting by Leonardo Da Vinci called *La belle ferroniere* (French: "The Beautiful Blacksmith's Wife"). It is now in the Louvre Museum in Paris.

Hairpin – A hairpin that is worn to hold a hairstyle. U-shaped with parallel and equal sides. They help to strengthen the hair.

Hatpins - hatpins began to be widely used after the disappearance of thread and ribbon jewelry. They are a piece of jewelry with a hat-like top part in the shape of a long needle. It was mainly used to fasten ladies hats.

Resilla - this jewelry has a design reminiscent of the appearance of a fishnet. It is mostly decorated with fine wires, pearls, corals, and precious stones. This term means "net" in French. With the help of *rasilla*, women could put their hair in it. In the 1940s, it is said that he returned to the tradition.

Sarpech is a turban ornament worn by Indian nobility. Its vertical part is "*jigha*" in the shape of a flower, and its horizontal part is called "*sarpati*". *Sarpech* word "*sar*" means "head", and "*pech*" means "pin" on the front side of the turban. In Western countries, a headpiece similar to it is called an *aigrette*. In Old Persian it was called *jikka* or *jiqa*. In Turkey, it is called *Sarguch*.

Wreath is a head ornament in the form of a wreath. It is mainly an ornament in the form of laurel, oak, olive or ivy leaves. It was given more to honor the winners of Olympia. Golden wreaths were also worn as crowns by Etruscan rulers and Roman emperors.

Among them, *Acus*, *Aigrette*, *Bandeau*, *Barrette*, *Benoiton*, *Billiment*, *Bodkin*, *Diadem*, *Resilla* are transliteration methods. In the translation, their alternative is given using the letters of the translated language.

In jewelry lexemes such as *hairpin*, *hatpin*, and *sarpech*, the method of calque is observed. The word *hairpin* consist of “hair” which means human parts of body and “pin” means to fasten something. The *hairpin* is a jewelry utilized by women to clip the hair. It is translated word by word. The word *hatpin* is also made by two words. *Hat* is a women headwear and *hatpin* is used to hold the hat. The word *sarpech* is composed by two words. “Sar” means head and “pech” means “to pin”. In these examples we can see the calque method.

Speaking of translation, it is necessary to dwell on the lexicon without an alternative. Non-alternative lexicon is the absence of lexical units in one language in whole or in part in another language. Non-alternative lexicon includes concepts specific to the national culture of a particular nation. Non-alternative lexis includes proper nouns, realias, lacunae. Realia is also included in the scope of the concept of non-alternative lexicon. Realia is studied in linguistics. Realia means "real" - "true". Realias are words and word combinations that represent events related to the life, lifestyle, customs, and culture of a particular people, and they have a national and periodic character. In the jewelry terminology of the Uzbek language, realias make up many vocabulary words. For example;

Tillakosh is an ornament worn on the forehead by women. In some Russian-language sources, it is given as "ТИЛЛЯ КОШ". In English sources it is also referred to as "tilla kosh". In other languages, it is used in the form of tillakosh. An ornate forehead ornament made of gold.

Takyatuzi is found in Russian-language sources as "такядузи". It is one of women's head ornaments.

Shibirma is presented in the Russian source as "шибирма". An ancient earring with a big eye in the middle. It's an ancient earring of Bukhara.

Mohitillo is presented in the Russian source as "мохи тилло". Women's forehead jewelry. Half-moon shaped jewelry.

Gajak - in the Russian language source it is given as "гажак". This is also a piece of jewelry with the image of a bird. Almond-shaped jewelry made of silver. It has many meanings. For example;

1. Curly
2. Duck feather
3. Plant sprouts.

Tillabargak is a jewelry widely used by women at the beginning of the 20th century. In the source in English, the definition of "golden leaf" is given about it.

Manglaytuzi is a women's headdress. Osmatuzi is also a headpiece.

Bodomoy is presented in the Russian-language sources as "бодомой". It's an pendant.

Bibishakh – (bibi-mother, shakh-horn) is a head ornament reminiscent of women's forehead jewelry. In the English-language source, it is given in the form of "bibishokh".

Butuntirnok - in Russian-language sources it is "бутун туннак". An ornament worn on the temple.

Tavq - (Arabic word which means a ring in bird's neck) - women's necklace. Tavq consists of four-leafed flowers and patterns. In it, the embossed shape of the bird is clearly created.

Bozuband is a bozvant women's jewelry. It is hung on the neck or armpit.

Cylindrical amulet. It was very popular among Uzbek people.

Zebigardon is a belt that women wear around the neck and fall on the chest. One of the ancient jewels. It has a square, circular shape.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that jewelry terms in English and Uzbek languages are translated in different ways. Transliteration, calque methods were used in the translation of some jewelry lexemes. Realias in languages cannot be translated into other languages. Realias are only related to the culture of a certain nation.

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